

THE ROLE OF STUDENT ASSOCIATIONS IN RELATION TO PEACE IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS (AN ANALYTICAL STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO SINDH PROVINCE)

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Abstract

Today's advanced educational institutes have witnessed tremendous growth in political, social, economic and scientific fields. On the contrary, current society issues show that the world lacking the peace and people are facing the problems of social injustice, immorality and in-security similar to the era fourteen hundred years ago. Students associations play vital role in peace building in the institutes. Throughout history of Sindh, several student unions have served as catalysts and played an impressive part in a verity of crucial issues. The restriction was imposed due to on campus violence among student organizations. This study investigates a comparative analysis of role played by student unions in relation to peace in educational institutions in Sindh. This study uses secondary data of educational institutions of Sindh. Two major higher educational institutions are taken as a sample. The methodology employed is documentary research design. The findings reflect negative impact on educational institutions caused by student unions. It is recommended based on findings that a constructive role of student unions can be ensured by withdrawing their affiliation with mainstream and anti-national political parties. Further it is recommended that manifestos of student unions must abide by the law of the land.

1. INTRODUCTION

Educational institutions are cradles for the nourishment of future leaders. Student unions working in educational institutions are the nurseries to produce leadership for tomorrow. In order to foster healthy democratic behaviors among the youth, the role of student unions is of vital importance as it engages the youthful age of individuals when they are in making and shaping process. It is important understand that 66% population of Pakistan consists of youngsters. This huge chunk of population with energy and talent can't remain untapped and if remains untapped, it will explore the avenues of violence and crime. Student unions are the

platforms to unleash and engage the talent of the youngsters.

Democracy and Student unions are strongly connected. During the first few years of Pakistan's existence, students were active participants in politics and guardians of the general public's interests. Student protests were the catalyst for the 1968 mass movement that eventually destroyed in Ayub Khan's rule. After progressive and anti-dictatorial alliances swept the 1983 union polls, even ZiaulHaq felt threatened by student power and banned student unions in 1984. In 1989, Benazir Bhutto reestablished student unions for a brief while before they were dissolved under the

pretence of the Supreme Court's 1993 judgment, never to be seen again.

Despite a stormy history and empty promises from the halls of power, students have managed to gain a foothold in politics. The 'Student Solidarity March,' a recent wave of developing student politics is an expression of this reality. In 2019, the march was held in 50 cities across Pakistan, compared to nine in 2018. Students gathered in large numbers to demand the re-establishment of student unions and the resolution of grievances. Students and educational institutions were given the opportunity to speak on issues that are important to them. These included (but were not limited to) sexual harassment on universities, the administration's coercive attitude, low budget allocation to education and the Higher Education Commission (HEC), and law enforcement agencies policing campuses.

The banning of student unions also led to pan-Islamic religious trends on campuses and a rise in extremism and intolerance at universities in Pakistan. A trend observed over several years suggests that student organizations displace unions that primarily serve the purposes and agendas of their parents' political or religious parties and do not care much to the student problems, such as lack of facilities on campus and dormitories, the wave of continuing tuition increases, transportation and the alienation of students from curriculum design or the lack of career counseling facilities for students.

2. Historical Background

Historically, Pakistan has no good experience with politics as major chunk of ruling eras have been nondemocratic military rules, consequently, no enabling environment has ever existed for the smooth functioning of student unions. A country with no democratic environment in its main stream politics is in deficit of producing democratic and peaceful functioning students unions. Therefore, historically the students unions and their role for peace building and abhorring violence have been in doldrums.

In the past, students' unions were banned by General Zia- Ul-Haq, the military dictator of Pakistan in 1984 as his brutal government had to face opposition. However it can be said that these unions still do exist in most of the

institutions. Our youth has been going through many challenges from beginning. Our institutions have forced episodes of bloodshed from the establishment of Pakistan. Intolerance has been growing among the students. However, political parties also involve them in atrocious physical violence. On 24th October 2018, the National Counter Terrorism Authority (NACTA) and Higher Education Commission (HEC) signed MoU to prevent violence and irrationality (Worldtimes.com). Students Union is a council of students that involve students in societal activities and protect their rights. In India and Pakistan, these unions are used as pressure groups (Casstt.com). Many individuals are against the idea of student's unions, which isn't correct. These unions play a very important role in protesting to improve their transport, hostel, academic, peaceful stay at University and mess facilities. Students' unions only include student members and accept no strangers. They provide assistance to students and fight for their rights. They stand against political, religious, sexual and social discrimination. They are the in-charge of students' social life. (Brainly.com). Such kind of engagement motivate students to develop and achieve more confidence, decisiveness and administration that can shape their careers and adult lives (mankato.mnsu.edu).

Mashal Khan, a journalism student, was arrested by religious classmates on the campus of Abdul Wali Khan University in Mardan, Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa province in March 2019. He was charged with blasphemy, which was later released as a baseless allegation. Also in March 2019, a student at Islamia University-affiliated Government Sadiq Egerton College in Punjab's Bahawalpur city stabbed his professor to death over alleged blasphemy. According to the news reports, incidents of violence were reported mainly at Punjab University in Lahore, University of Karachi, Quaid-i-Azam University in Islamabad, International Islamic University in Islamabad and the Islamabad-based Federal Urdu University of arts, science and technology. Pakistani students protested this month to re-establish student unions, banned by then-Pakistani military dictator Muhammad Zia-ul-Haq in 1984. (University World News)

3. Rational of the Study

The very panacea to the national issues especially peace building is the vibrant and democratic prevalence of student unions. The banning of student unions have served no purpose of discouraging violence but it has lapsed the opportunity of producing visionary leaders at national level.

Pakistani students protested twice in Pakistan to re-establish student unions, banned by then-Pakistani military dictator Muhammad Zia-ul-Haq in 1984. First time on November 30, 2018 and another time on 29th November 2019. They are encouraged by the initiative taken by the province of Sindh, which became the first to restore student unions through a bill passed by the provincial parliament on 11 February 2022, described as a “historic move” of provincial government ministers. The bill passed unanimously by the Sindh Provincial Parliament would force all educational institutions, private and public, to hold annual elections allowing students to choose their representatives to look after their students' studies, extracurricular or other hobbies. Under the new law, educational institutions must have at least one student union member in their federation, senate or council. Sindh's bill has been supported by opposition parties in the House and welcomed by students from all provinces, who have called on other provincial governments to allow student unions. Pakistan has more than 58 student organizations, 30 of which are affiliated with political, ethnic or religious parties, but these organizations have no legal status on campus and no representation in the decision-making body of university governing bodies. The Sindh Bill was first proposed in 2019, a year marked by student protests calling for the revival of student unions. For two years, the Sindh Parliament Standing Committee on Law, Parliamentary Affairs and Human Rights held consultations on the plan with all stakeholders, including university rectors, educators, and teachers, related education, representatives of political parties and their allied student organizations. The lifting of the ban on student unions has been in the manifesto of every major political party since Zia-ul-Haq ended his rule in 1988, but the promise was never kept. It is now widely accepted in Pakistan that social evils on campus emerged in 1984 when student

unions were banned and the solution to problems such as harassment of female students, increasing violence, intolerance and extremism on campus lies in restoring student unions. With the move from Sindh province, “It will be difficult for other provinces to continue to curb this demand for students”, experts said. Various civil society organizations and members of various political parties expressed solidarity with the student protesters and called on the government to restore unions.

4. Literature Review

On February 17, after the passage of the Sindh Bill, Pakistan People's Party's chairman Bilawal Bhutto Zardari spoke at a student conference in Karachi, the capital of Sindh and stated that political activism in colleges and universities would not only empower the voice of students demanding their rights, but it would also strengthen the institutions, their disciplines and the quality of education. He also noted an increase in cases of sexual harassment on campus, which he attributed to the absence of student unions. His comments on the rise of harassment on campus are endorsed by many human rights activists and student representatives.

Raja Ashraf, vice-chair of the Punjab chapter of the Human Rights Commission of Pakistan, told University World News: “Students are not part of the membership of anti-harassment committees at colleges and universities; they are not consulted before decisions [are made] affecting their life and careers; they are not involved in politics; they are beaten when they protest for their rights; and sent behind bars when they challenge oppressive policies of the rules introduced by dictators.”

PPP member of the National Assembly, Shazia Marri, stated to University World News: “The absence of student unions has led to a rise in harassment cases in universities and has stifled freedom of expression leading to violence at campuses.”

According to Pakistan's Daily Times newspaper, the Islamabad-based Dukhtar Foundation launched a helpline to facilitate the filing of harassment cases in 2018.

Two years of data shows that 20,741 cases were reported, of which a whopping 82% (16,981 complaints) were filed by female students at

universities from across Pakistan, often against teachers. Harassment of female students on campus, related to the lack of student unions, is also a national concern. It also comes amid a general failure of universities to implement anti-harassment rules. The student wing of political and religious parties at universities is mostly or entirely male, and female student participation in administrative work on campus is minimal to the point of non-existence.

While the link between student union absences and campus harassment is of recent concern, others have pointed to broader benefits of student unions, especially in terms of life of civic life. She PPP's Marri said "student unions provide training to sharpen the analytical thinking of students which can provide ground for well-groomed leaders of the future".

Before the 1984 ban, several student unionists rose to prominence in politics, and some are now ministers or hold positions in their respective parties. Marri said: banning freedom of association for students is an attempt by autocratic rulers to keep younger generations subjected to their oppressive policies.

Journalist Asma Shirazi, who hosts a TV show and writes for the BBC Urdu service, told University World News that banning student unions has caused huge damage to politics in Pakistan as the move "Blocked the way for the emergence of a new political leadership as student unions earlier proved to be nurseries for well-groomed politicians".

She said: "Dictators and political leaders with a dictatorial mind are always fearful of the power of students as they have seen how students can shake the corridors of power".

Former president Ayub Khan, a military dictator in Pakistan who took power in a 1958 coup, was forced to resign in 1969 after massive protests, mainly by university students. (The role of the students in ousting him was researched in a 2013 study by Aileen Eisenberg, published by the Global Nonviolent Action Database).

Research shows that university students have adopted nonviolent methods such as staging anti-government plays and organizing protests in different cities organized by the National Student Federation and Student Action Committee student movement of the time organizing and leading, which was formed after the deaths of three university students in 1968

during an anti-government student protest in Rawalpindi.

Martial law was introduced in Pakistan in 1958 and all types of unions, including student unions, were banned for two years. This led to the strengthening of student unions of religious parties such as the Islami Jamiat-e-Talaba (IJT) of Jamaat-i-Islami, a religio-political rightist party which became the main opponent of progressive or leftist student organizations which were against the military rule in Pakistan.

PPP, the late Zulfikar Ali Bhutto, led the political uprising against the military dictator. Student politics flourished when he came to power in 1971 until he was executed by another military dictator, ZiaulHaq, in 1979.

The results of a student union election in 1983 sent shockwaves through the dictatorship, seeing students become a major power and an emerging threat to the military rule, like the situation faced by Ayub Khan. As a result, Zia-ul-Haq banned student unions in Pakistan in 1984.

Razia Sultana, professor of history at Quaid-i-Azam University Islamabad, explained to University World News: "The rise of Islamic student movements at campuses was mainly due to the policies of former military dictator Zia-ul-Haq who favored such student organizations to counter the influence of leftist student movements which had led to the ouster of military dictator Ayub Khan and also because Zia-ul-Haq seized power from Zulfikar Ali Bhutto who was supported by socialist student.

It's worth mentioning that a huge number of current mainstream political leaders were once student representatives. Javed Hashmi, Jahangir Badar, and Liaquat Baloch are just a few of the many students who have risen through the ranks of student organizations to become politicians. Thousands of others were not permitted to practice their profession on college campuses and may not have sided with the mainstream parties. Indeed, if a progressive political culture could exist in college and university campuses, our mainstream political parties' willingness to accept a military-dominated political system would be less obvious.

5. Research Objectives

To explore the history of Student Unions

To investigate state's approach towards student unions

To analyze the role of student unions in upholding peace in Sindh

6. Research Methodology

The research methodology used to conduct this study is based on historical and documentary research. Secondary data is used to explore pros and cons of student unions and their role to maintain peace. The data sample consists of the higher education of Sindh and incidents reported in various print and electronic media houses. The incidents are comparatively analyzed to conclude about the role of student unions in peace building. This study will assist teachers, students, policy makers to understand the pros and cons of students unions historically in Pakistani perspective. And invite them to ponder upon the avenues to engage prime age of youngsters in nation and peace building.

7. Comparative Analysis

Roles and functioning of students unions have always been impacted by national and international politics whether rightist or leftist. International dynamics of political thought have influenced and encouraged student unions to pursue philosophy of peace or violence. With the rise of USSR we see heavy influence of leftist notions on student unions leading to violent and sanguinary struggle against capitalists.

Cold war between two super powers from 1950 to 1990 divided student politics into socialist and capitalist and rightist v/s leftist. Student unions during Ayub era went through notions of communist philosophies of red revolution which entrenched the philosophy of violent revolution to topple the capitalist regimes. Ayub era witnessed anti one unit violent student union politics bringing more violence into campus.

In the wake of Afghan Jihad in Afghanistan, students unions witnessed the rise of religious influence student politics which led the Pakistani society towards Islamisation. This divided society on leftist and religious grounds into deep stratification of political thought and such impact can be seen on student unions too. Islamisation brought with it pan Islamic revivalist inclinations among student unions under the umbrella of mainstream religious parties. This declined the effect of progressive and moderate political attitudes within students.

After the removal of Z.A Bhutto and his hanging universities in Sindh came under the surge of anti nationalist notions which were defiant of national integration. This defiant notion was multiplied with Soviet red revolution philosophy of grabbing the power at any level with violence and combatant struggle. Philosophical and ideological pretext gave multifold force to the clandestine student unions forums to raise the voice and shake the existence of state of Pakistan. Populist mandate given to ZA Bhutto and Sindh being its stronghold brought Sindh educational institutions at the helm of crisis and academic environment was eroded and student unions lost their true colors by adopting the agenda of being the proxy of mainstream political parties. University of Sindh and Liaquat Medical College were the hub of political activities predominantly anti Zia regime and some factions working against the state.

9/11 brought extremist and religious fanaticism into student politics. Super power of the time invading neighboring country of Pakistan with the intent to curb the ideology which she created during Russian invasion of Afghanistan. It was total turning around of state policy of Pakistan as the Kashmir Jihad was in progress and shunning an ideology which state has supported for two decades created ideological war within the country and impacting the very fabric of student unions. Universities in Sindh were also affected by the ideological shift and progressive and moderate student union forces were given support to dilute the impact of religious and sectarian political forces existing in campuses.

Such turns and twists at ideological level made the trudging of student union politics in universities of Pakistan especially Sindh more complicated and retarding. Some of the references can be discussed as following:

A Sindhi Hindu female medical student, Nimrita Kumari, was raped and killed at Bibi Aseefa Dental College (affiliated with Shaheed Mohtarma Benazir Bhutto Medical University) in Larkana city in 2019. Then on November 24th 2021, Nosheen Kazmi, a fourth year MBBS student at Chandka Medical College was found hanging from the ceiling fan in her hostel room. Then come Parveen Rind's (2022) eye opening allegations. Perveen is a nursing student and house officer at PUMHS Nawabshah who

alleges she was threatened and harassed sexually by three officials at the University who locked her in her hostel room and brutally beat her in order to make her comply with their unethical demands. Perveen Rind for her part claims that the spate of suicides of female students in Sindh's campuses are in fact murders carried out by rapists, harassers and murderers who she alleges operate with collusion of the administration.

Suicidal death of Naila Rind 2019 and Harassment complaints by Almas Behan 2022 in University of Sindh also went unheard and unnoticed with the passage of time.

In June 2021, a male university student was raped by two male students at a hostel at International Islamic University Islamabad, and in 2006 human rights organizations protested at a rape attempt on a female student of law at the University of Karachi which involved three members of the Islamic learning department (ILD) and one student of the physics department.

In November 2019, national events require the recovery of the students' unions and ended harassment and many students were arrested and expelled, while criminal accusations were set against 300 students, who organized or participated in protests held at 38 cities under the banner of the "Student Solidarity March".

In the absence of a student voice, harassment cases are often decided against the complainant. In 2020, Amna Ashfaq from the Department of Political Science at Islamia College, Peshawar complained about sexual harassment from her professor Amir Ullah Khan, but the investigation committee, comprising his colleagues, cleared him of the allegation. The students then resorted to protests and the case was subsequently decided last year by the ombudsman's office, which recommended firing the teacher.

In 2019, female students protested harassment by university officials at the University of Balochistan in Quetta but were heard only after the High Court of Balochistan ordered an investigation into a video scandal involving secret recordings to blackmail the students. Many female students dropped out of school following the scandal due to religious and tribal values in the area.

It's worth keeping in mind that political bodies will only be as active and responsive as the public demands. Our political parties, too, are a reflection of what they should be, with the loss of student and trade unions, culture and art, and independent intellectual activity.

Only a few years after Pakistan's independence, the Democratic Students Federation (DSF), led by Mohammad Sarwar, a student at Karachi's prestigious Dow Medical College (DMC), initiated a movement that sent concussive blasts through the political establishment. On January 8, 1953, police opened fire on a parade headed by DSF outside the Paradise Cinema in the heart of city, seven students and a minor were killed. Karachi went on strike on January 9 in protest of police brutality, and Khawaja Nazimuddin was forced to impose a curfew in the city for a few days, demonstrating how bad the situation had become following the police shooting.

The incident shocked the public and the intelligentsia so much that renowned poets such as Faiz Ahmed Faiz, Mustafa Zaidi, Saroor Barabankvi, and Nazish Amrohvi wrote poems about the murder of innocent students, and Prime Minister Khawaja Nazimuddin was forced to accept all of the students' demands, along with the establishment of a university of Karachi. In 1971, when numerous student activists from the National Students Federation (NSF) and the Sindh National Students Federation (SNSF) were imprisoned and tortured by the authorities in the former East Pakistan, Karachi students should be praised for standing up to the slaughter. Hidayat Hussain, Tanveer Sheikh, and Shahid Hussain were among the student activists arrested in 1971.

In 1978, Altaf Hussain and Azeem Tariq founded the All Pakistan Muhajir Students Organization (APMSO), which prepared the way for the Muhajir Qaumi Movement (MQM), which later changed its name to Muttahida Qaumi Movement, and student politics was tainted by ethnicity and terror.

Sindh University gripped by insecurity

According to Jan Khaskheli for The News, Sindh University in Jamshoro, Pakistan, is presently experiencing a law and order issues as accused criminals with the help of certain political parties have gone on the rampage and have resorted to attacking instructors.

Following the gruesome murder of Professor Bashir Channer, the university's director of student affairs, on January 2, 2012 Sajjid Memon, the director of campus security, is apparently receiving death threats, according to officials. This has alarmed for teachers, who are frequently threatened and abused in the classroom. The assassination of Channer highlighted institutional failure and a lack of protection, leaving teachers vulnerable. Channer had suspended 21 students who are linked with various political organizations, according to a relative, based on recommendations from a monitoring committee comprised of university authorities and political parties. The parties had given the committee permission to take action against them. Channer had been approached by several students, who insisted that they should be restored or suffer terrible consequences. Channer had turned down the offer. No one has come forward to claim responsibility for the killing.

Pakistan Universities reel under rising student lawlessness

12 students were injured in an armed conflict between two groups at Karachi University in February of this year, which has seen a succession of violent attacks in the previous three years. In December 2012, due to a bomb explosion on campus four students have been injured. The bomb was placed near the cafeteria with the intention of killing students from a competing gang.

Kidnappings, shootings, killings, and smashing and burning university property have all been reported, and universities have been forced to be closed for many days in each case.

Reasons behind the violence

According to academics, campus violence is on the rise as a result of student organization' connected to political parties, which give them funding, guns, and security.

"The role of weaponry in national politics has greatly expanded, and these young students are an easy target for politicians," said Anis Ahmed, vice-chancellor of Riphah International University, to University World News.

"They provide them with security and resources in order to achieve political power." "Young

people are enticed into a fascinating life, then exploited for greater political gain through illicit means," Ahmed explained. Arif Azeem of Karachi University reinforced this sentiment, noting that while the university's administrators were aware of the 'problem students,' they "couldn't do anything against them because they fear for their own security, because the controllers of these gangs are big political leaders."

Although the current administration repealed a ban on student unions in 2008, they are still not formally allowed at institutions.

Academics had conflicting views to the proposal, with some hailing it as a step to politics colleges and others dismissing it as such. Many academics support student unions, but they do not want them to be politically motivated. According to Islamabad-based professor Arshad Saleem, the time of typical student unions is over, and in today's Pakistan, "weapons will be the order of the day, and institutions will become theatres for political wrestling."

Students at war with on another

Armed clashes at universities have a long history, and they depict the story of politically or ideologically opposed groups at odds with one another.

A conflict between the People's Students' Federation and the Punjabi Students' Association, for example, resulted in 12 students being harmed at Karachi University.

APMSO, which is affiliated to Sindh's ruling alliance, is accused by IJT of torturing and killing one of its activists. In 2008, police recovered a massive weapons cache, including Kalashnikovs and hand grenades, at Punjab University, blaming IJT for multiple incidents.

Some student groups are connected to violent forces such as the Taliban or Jamat-ud-Dawa, which was responsible for the 2008 Mumbai bombings.

The bombing at Karachi University, which harmed ISO students, was committed by Taliban-affiliated students. In May of last year, police announced the arrest of 04 Taliban members, one of them was a student.

Not only at major universities, but also there has been violence at countless other public places around the country.

Six students were injured in a clash between the Pakhtun Students' Federation (PSF) and the ISO at the Federal Urdu University of Arts, Science, and Technology in Karachi in April last year, while seven students were injured in a battle between the IJT and the PSF in July last year. In May of last year, ten IJT students at Multan's Bahauddin Zakariya University were severely wounded when PSF supporters attacked them. "Police were powerless to intervene because the PSF is a member of the ruling party, and Multan is the prime minister's electoral area." We can't do anything because they're powerful than us," stated a professor who didn't want to be identified.

IT student Deen Muhammad was killed by students from an enemy army team at Sindh University in Jamshoro on 7 March of this year, while 15 students were critically injured in a battle at Karachi's NED University in July last year.

8. Conclusions

Upon pondering over variety of incidents reported through reliable sources following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Students unions play a constructive role by working as a bridge between administration and students. The bond is shaken when outside influences make their way in decision making of student unions
2. Students union remain impartial stakeholder in higher education institutions as long as they are not hijacked by any political force hailing from mainstream or regional political entity
3. Role of student union in propagating peace remains intact when they work as reformist and philanthropist. The same role is maligned when student unions work as pressure groups to coerce administration to favor them beyond the threshold.
4. Role of student unions become stark when financial embezzlement take place in the ranks and files of unions paving the way for vested interests to pull the strings of student bodies in promoting violence in the campuses.
5. Peace remains priority of a student union when their manifesto enshrines the harmony and diversity, consequently, union will pursue the path of tolerance and peaceful co existence.

6. Vibrant student union can only exist and survive when there is democratic environment within the union itself. All the office bearers are elected through fair and transparent elections conducted within the union. As a result union will have representatives who have a mandate of the members and students. The mandate will empower them to ensure peace and harmony at the campus.

7. Role of student union is compromised and dubious when it functions on non democratic norms as their representatives are selected from any other political party

8. Student unions can become dangerous when they are influenced and motivated by anti state ideologies. They so called nationalist in garb of ethnicity, language and provincialism can transform youth student unions into state dividing force.

9. Teenage and youth are the phases of life which can be molded constructive and destructive as well. Infusing constructive leadership skills at this age can produce positive individuals who can contribute to peace building and nation building. The role of student unions has been flawed in providing conducive environment to youth in order to produce constructive individuals.

10. Lack of ownership by higher education institutions to student unions has created a gap of understanding and working relation as a result higher education institutions treat student unions as a pressure groups rather that extended supportive arm to bridge gap between student and university administrations.

9. Recommendations

Based on the findings from documentary evidence and media reports following recommendations can be useful for policy makers, educationists, administrators and student representatives:

1. Students unions must be democratic in electing their bodies.
2. The manifesto of students unions must be in line with the constitution of Pakistan and law of the land.
3. A national emancipation drive for constructive role of youth in politics may be launched so that youngsters may get mainstream politics approach

4. Peaceful co existence and national harmony may be made mandatory part of syllabus taught at various level of education system.

5. Diversity and tolerance may be the themes of national curriculum and syllabus of higher education institution.

6. It is observed that political fanaticism and polarization disrupts peace and tranquility in the campuses and ultimately society.

7. Political intolerance and extremism within society can be controlled when healthy democratic attitudes are encouraged in the counseling sessions of students unions

8. A national level body may be formed for registration of student unions. This authority should have well defined frame work for registering and recognizing student unions. It will lead well documented working of student unions.

9. Student unions and their representative may be given international collaboration like exchange programs and model conferences where they can interact with international students and acquire first hand experience of working of other student unions in other countries. It will broaden and transform the vision of student union representatives and they can adopt new trends prevailing in the world for the functioning of student unions.

10. Students unions may work on a time line and may be given extension of functioning based on their performance. The key performance indicators must encompass both academic and administrative as well. Based on their academic support performance, there can be reward and punishment. This will set effective accountability system in order to regulate the student unions as a trouble shooter body rather than trouble making body.

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